

Inertial sensor-based analysis of motor synchronization strategies in collaborative tasks

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Introduction

Collaborative task for motor and cognitive rehabilitation aims to improve individual training by involving participants in active collaboration to achieve a **common goal**, without predefined role assignments [1]. While scientific literature has explored these concepts with pairs of participants (dyads), the **upscaling of collaborative rehabilitation** to include more people requires novel approaches and technologies, as pursued in the **MYRTUS EU project** to enable several users to participate in real-time training sessions remotely.

Objective: This study focuses on analyzing the **synchronization strategies** adopted by **dyads** and **triads** performing a synchronization task. This task is foundational to a Virtual Reality (VR) exergame where participants act as dragon-boat paddlers navigating a maze river.

Materials and Methods

25 unaffected and right-handed participants (23 ± 3 years old) were randomly assigned to 10 groups, consisting of five dyads and five triads.

The motor task was a planar point-to-point frontal movement (back-and-forth) between two targets at different speeds. Participants of the same group were asked to **collaboratively** reach the target speed by **synchronizing** their arm's movements.

Each participant wore an **Xsens MTw magneto-inertial measurement unit (MIMUs)** on their right wrist, live streaming the orientation and angular velocity at 100 Hz.

Input kinematic data

Angular orientation around Z-axis

Angular velocity around Z-axis

Data processing for synchronization metrics extraction

First metric: Phase Alignment

- Angular orientation signals $\theta^{(i)}$ from all participants
- Sliding-window Pearson correlation (r_{group}), where the window length is dynamically fixed to the group's movement period (T_{mov})
- Synchronization criteria:
 - $r_{group} > 0.7$
 - AND this condition persists for at least $2 * T_{mov}$
- It quantifies the **group synchrony**

$$r_{group}(t) = \frac{1}{\binom{N}{2}} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=1}^N R_{ij}$$

$$R_{ij}(t) = \frac{\sum_{k=t}^{t+W-1} (\theta^{(i)}(t_k) - \bar{\theta}_W^{(i)}(t)) (\theta^{(j)}(t_k) - \bar{\theta}_W^{(j)}(t))}{\sqrt{\sum_{k=t}^{t+W-1} (\theta^{(i)}(t_k) - \bar{\theta}_W^{(i)}(t))^2 \sum_{k=t}^{t+W-1} (\theta^{(j)}(t_k) - \bar{\theta}_W^{(j)}(t))^2}}$$

Second metric: Speed Convergence

- Group-averaged speed of all participants $\|\omega\|(t)$
- a moving average is applied with a window size $T_{mov} \rightarrow \|\omega\|_{smooth}(t)$
- Convergence criteria:

$$\|\omega\|_{smooth}(t) - v_{target} < \epsilon_v$$

$$\epsilon_v = 5 \text{ deg/s}$$
- It quantifies how quickly the group collaboratively achieves the target angular velocity

$$group \text{ speed} = \|\omega\|(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\omega_{x,i}^2(t) + \omega_{y,i}^2(t) + \omega_{z,i}^2(t)}$$

$$smoothed \text{ speed} = \|\omega\|_{smooth}(t) = \frac{1}{W} \sum_{k=t-\frac{W-1}{2}}^{t+\frac{W-1}{2}} \|\omega\|(t-k)$$

Synchronization indicator

- TimeToSynchPhase [s]:** the first time instant at which a window begins that satisfies the Synchronization criteria
- TimeToSynchVel [s]:** the first time instant the Convergence Criterion is met

Results

Conclusions

We compared synchronization times between dyads and triads across different target velocities. Phase synchronization was successfully achieved with comparable timings between dyads and triads. In addition, participants converged to the target velocity both in dyads and triads, and slightly earlier in triads (9.4 ± 5.3 s vs 11.0 ± 6.4 s). The trend of the TimeToSynchVel showed a decreasing pattern in both groups. These findings suggest that group size differently affects phase and angular velocity synchronization. Future work will explore scalability also on tetrads.

REFERENCES

[1] A. Takagi et al. eLife 2019;8:e41328.